

GP4 FUR4SUSTAIN NEWSLETTER

COST Action CA 18220

FUR4SUSTAIN CHAIR MESSAGE

Last year, as a balance, was a really smooth and joyful year for FUR4Sustain. We were able to meet in Thessaloniki for fruitful consolidation of the network and also in Graz for an insightful Training School on 'From Green to Sustainability Chemistry', enhance science research through STSMs and train the Youngest of the network via (Young) Happy Hour events. The challenges are already knocking at our door, with FUR4Sustain COST Action reaching (almost!) its end!

GRAZ TRAINING SCHOOL

The last FUR4Sustain Training School took place at the University of Graz in Austria and online. The main objective of the Training School was to cover the spectrum from Green Chemistry actions to potential dynamics and consequences in global systems.

The concept of (Circular) Green Chemistry and its implementation in practice was discussed, including several examples from the laboratory to the market scale. A particular focus was placed on sustainability assessments (e.g., LCA) and systemic approaches for analysing possible consequences of biorefinery innovations at different levels.

The Training School included exciting lectures and interactive courses by high-level trainers from academia and industry, excursions, and a social program.

5TH HAPPY HOUR

Why Systems Thinking Made a Chemist Worry about Separations?

The success of Happy Hours continued in March, when we had the honour to talk with Philip Jessop, the Canada Research Chair of Green Chemistry at Queen's University in Canada and the Executive Research Director of Forward Water Technologies Inc.

GRANTS AWARDED

GRANT AWARDING COORDINATOR MESSAGE - DR. RUPERT KARGL

-The Grant Period 4 has witnessed the creation of a tremendous variety of new ideas and results thanks to the interactions made possible by our COST action. I am confident that this will also be the case for the coming period when Fur4Sustain will put these creations into new products and processes for the benefit of the European community.

FUR4Sustain CA was able to award 24 grantees in GP4:

- 14 STSM grants
- 5 ITC Conference grants
- 3 Dissemination Conference grants
- 1 Virtual Mobility grant
- 1 Virtual Networking Support grant

These grants are crucial for young researchers, as highlighted by Simão's experience when we asked him about the benefits of his STSM grant.

-The STSM not only allowed me to explore different scientific techniques but also, at the same level of importance, taught me that to have success, we as scientists must have communication and networking skills to discuss and make possible the upgrading of our work. This kind of activity gives young researchers the right opportunities to evolve and open their minds for the future.

THESSALONIKI MC/CG/WG MEETING

The Fur4Sustain annual meeting took place in Thessaloniki, featuring presentations by invited speakers Dr Fr. Jérôme, Assoc. Pr. G. Z. Papageorgiou and Dr I. Deligkiozi. They covered various aspects of biobased materials, from biomass conversion to the synthesis of biobased polymers and finally the business and funding opportunities for biobased materials.

Scientific actors from all WGs presented their work and representatives from 5 companies shared insights in advancing sustainable solutions and products to the market.

2ND YOUNG HAPPY HOUR

This year's YOUNG Happy Hour featured a special session on tips and tricks for writing successful Marie Curie Fellowship proposals. Renowned evaluators and former fellows generously shared their invaluable insights and experiences.

As usual, our young FUR4Sustain scientists wowed the audience with their impressive work in 3 WG of the Action, which focused on bioeconomy, monomers, polymer synthesis and characterization, and recycling. It was a morning full of inspiration and knowledge sharing!

GP4 VIDEOS

- 5th FUR4Sustain Happy Hour - Philip Jessop <https://youtu.be/-Vqeg7WadGE?si=1bCamJlgaKDILQhl>
- 2nd Young Happy Hour <https://youtu.be/A1tLcGoz8Kg>

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COST (European Cooperation in Science and Technology) is a funding agency for research and innovation networks. Our Actions help connect research initiatives across Europe and enable scientists to grow their ideas by sharing them with their peers. This boosts their research, career and innovation.